

THE PRACTICALITY OF SHIFTED PRIMES

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Received: 1/18/18, Accepted: 11/8/18, Published: 11/23/18

Abstract

A natural number n is called *practical* if every integer between 1 and n can be expressed as a sum of distinct positive divisors of n . In this paper, given an integer a , we explore the practicality of shifted primes $p - a$. Let

$$P_a(x) := |\{p \leq x : p \text{ prime, } p - a \text{ practical}\}|.$$

We establish upper and lower bounds for $P_a(x)$. In particular, for any given odd integer a , there are infinitely many primes p such that $p - a$ is practical.

1. Introduction

A natural number n is called *practical* if every integer between 1 and n can be expressed as a sum of distinct positive divisors of n . These numbers were first introduced by Srinivasan [13] and have since been studied by several authors [2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18]. There are many similarities between the distribution of practical numbers and that of prime numbers. The analogues of Legendre's conjecture [5], Goldbach's conjecture [7], the twin prime conjecture [7], and the prime number theorem [18, 20], are all theorems in the context of practical numbers. More conjectures involving practical numbers can be found in [15].

The sequence of practical numbers, which begins with

$$1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 12, 16, 18, 20, 24, 28, 30, \dots,$$

seems to have many terms in common with the shifted primes $p - 1$:

$$1, 2, 4, 6, 10, 12, 16, 18, 22, 28, 30, \dots$$

This raises the question as to whether there are infinitely many primes p for which $p - 1$ is practical. The number of primes below x is $\sim x / \log x$, while the number of practical numbers below x is $\sim cx / \log x$ for some constant $1.311 < c < 1.693$ (see [18, 20]). Thus, it seems reasonable to expect that the number of primes $p \leq x$, for which $p - 1$ is practical, is asymptotic to $Cx / (\log x)^2$ for some positive constant C . Theorem 1 gives lower and upper bounds for the count of such primes. More generally, given an integer a , we explore the practicality of shifted primes $p - a$. Let

$$P_a(x) := |\{p \leq x : p \text{ prime, } p - a \text{ practical}\}|.$$

Since all practical numbers greater than one are even, only the case of odd a is of interest.

Theorem 1. *Let a be an odd integer. Let $\beta > 2 + 2e \log 2 = 5.7683\dots$ and $\delta = 1 - (1 + \log \log 2) / \log 2 = 0.086071\dots$ be the Erdős-Tenenbaum-Ford constant. We have*

$$\frac{x}{(\log x)^\beta} \ll P_a(x) \ll \frac{x}{(\log x)^{1+\delta}}.$$

We will prove a more general version of Theorem 1, which applies to other sequences besides the practical numbers. Given any arithmetic function θ , define the set $\mathcal{B}_\theta \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ as follows. Let $1 \in \mathcal{B}_\theta$ and let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} \cdots p_k^{\alpha_k} \in \mathcal{B}_\theta$, with primes $p_1 < \cdots < p_k$, if and only if

$$p_i \leq \theta(p_1^{\alpha_1} \cdots p_{i-1}^{\alpha_{i-1}}), \quad (1 \leq i \leq k). \tag{1}$$

Sierpinski [12] and Stewart [14] found that the set of practical numbers is precisely the set \mathcal{B}_θ with $\theta(n) = \sigma(n) + 1$, where $\sigma(n)$ denotes the sum of the positive divisors of n .

We shall write \mathcal{B}_0 to denote the set \mathcal{B}_θ with $\theta(n) = \max(2, n)$. Since $\max(2, n) \leq \sigma(n) + 1$, the set \mathcal{B}_0 is a subset of the set of practical numbers.

Theorem 2. *Let β and δ be as in Theorem 1. Assume θ satisfies $\max(2, n) \leq \theta(n) \leq n \exp(A(\log \log 3n)^{3/(2\delta)})$ for some constant A . Let \mathcal{S} be any set with $\mathcal{B}_0 \subseteq \mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{B}_\theta$ and write $S_a(x) := |\{p \leq x : p \text{ prime, } p - a \in \mathcal{S}\}|$. For any fixed odd integer a , we have*

$$\frac{x}{(\log x)^\beta} \ll S_a(x) \ll \frac{x}{(\log x)^{1+\delta}}.$$

These bounds remain valid under the weaker condition

$$\max(2, n) \leq \theta(n) \ll n \exp((\log n)^{o(1)}),$$

provided the exponent $1 + \delta$ is replaced by $1 + \delta - \varepsilon$ with any $\varepsilon > 0$.

Note that $3/(2\delta) = 17.427\dots$. Since $\sigma(n) + 1 \ll n \log \log 2n$, Theorem 1 follows from Theorem 2.

Besides the practical numbers, we mention two more examples of sets \mathcal{S} to which Theorem 2 applies. Given a fixed parameter $t \geq 2$, consider the set of positive integers whose ratios of consecutive divisors do not exceed t (see [10, 16, 18, 20]). These integers are called t -dense and are precisely the integers in the set \mathcal{B}_θ with $\theta(n) = tn$ (see [16, Lemma 2.2]).

Second, the φ -practical numbers, i.e., integers n such that the polynomial $X^n - 1$ has a divisor in $\mathbb{Z}[X]$ of every degree below n (see [9, 17]). Although this set is not equal to \mathcal{B}_θ for any θ , it satisfies $\mathcal{B}_0 \subset \mathcal{B}_{\theta_1} \subset \mathcal{S} \subset \mathcal{B}_{\theta_2}$, where $\theta_1(n) = n + 1$ and $\theta_2(n) = n + 2$.

The proof of the lower bound of Theorem 2 (see Proposition 1) rests on a Bombieri-Vinogradov type theorem (Lemma 1), due to Bombieri, Friedlander and Iwaniec, for primes in arithmetic progressions to large moduli [1]. To control for repeated counting of the same integer, we use a result by Norton [8] for the frequency of large values of the divisor function $\tau(n)$ (Lemma 2). The upper bound in Theorem 2 (see Proposition 2) follows from an upper bound by Ford [4] for the number of shifted primes with a divisor from an interval.

2. The Lower Bound

Proposition 1. *Let a be an odd integer and $\beta > 2 + 2e \log 2 = 5.768\dots$. The number of primes $p \leq x$, for which $p - a \in \mathcal{B}_0$, is*

$$\gg \frac{x}{(\log x)^\beta}.$$

We write $\log_2 x = \log \log x$ and $\log_3 x = \log \log \log x$.

Lemma 1 (Bombieri, Friedlander, Iwaniec [1]). *Let $a \neq 0$ be an integer and $A > 0$, $2 \leq Q \leq x^{3/4}$ be reals. Let \mathcal{Q} be the set of all integers q , relatively prime to a , from an interval $Q' < q \leq Q$. Then*

$$\sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \left| \pi(x; q, a) - \frac{\pi(x)}{\varphi(q)} \right| \leq \left\{ K \left(\theta - \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 xL^{-1} + O \left((xL^{-3}(\log_2 x)^2) \right) \right\} \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \frac{1}{\varphi(q)} + O(xL^{-A}),$$

where $\theta = \log Q / \log x$, $L = \log x$, K is absolute, the first implied constant in O depends only on A , and the second one on a and A .

Lemma 2 (Norton [8]). *Let $\tau(n)$ denote the number of positive divisors of the integer n . For $x \geq x_0$, $y \geq \log_2 x$,*

$$\#\{n \leq x : \tau(n) \geq 2^y\} \leq \frac{x}{\log x} \exp \left\{ -y \log y + y(\log_3 x + 1) + O \left(\frac{y}{\log_2 x} \right) \right\}.$$

The following observation follows immediately from the definition of the set \mathcal{B}_0 .

Lemma 3. *If $n \in \mathcal{B}_0$ and $1 \leq k \leq n$, then $nk \in \mathcal{B}_0$.*

Lemma 4. *Let a be an odd integer. There is a constant $\kappa = \kappa(a) > 1$, such that the number of integers $n \in \mathcal{B}_0 \cap [x, \kappa x]$, which are relatively prime to a , is*

$$\gg_a \frac{x}{\log x}.$$

Proof. Define

$$\mathcal{D}_{a,h}(x) = \{m = p_1^{\alpha_1} \cdots p_k^{\alpha_k} \leq x2^{-h} : P^+(|a|) < p_i \leq 2^h p_1^{\alpha_1} \cdots p_{i-1}^{\alpha_{i-1}}, 1 \leq i \leq k\},$$

where $p_1 < p_2 < \cdots < p_k$ are the prime factors of m . Here $P^+(n)$ denotes the largest prime factor of n and $P^+(1) = 1$. For each $m \in \mathcal{D}_{a,h}(x)$, we have $m2^h \in \mathcal{B}_0 \cap [1, x]$ and $\gcd(a, m2^h) = 1$, since a is odd and $P^+(|a|) < p_1$. The result now follows from an estimate due to Saias [11, Theorem 1], which shows that

$$|\mathcal{D}_{a,h}(x)| \asymp_{a,h} \frac{x}{\log x},$$

provided $h > h_0$ and $x > x_0$. □

Proof of Proposition 1. Let $\beta > 2 + 2e \log 2$ and put $c = (\beta - 2)/2 > e \log 2$. Let $\kappa > 1$ be the constant from Lemma 4. Define

$$\mathcal{Q}_a = \{q \in (\sqrt{x}, \kappa\sqrt{x}] : q \in \mathcal{B}_0, \gcd(q, a) = 1, \tau(q) \leq (\log x)^c\}.$$

By Lemma 2, the number of $n \leq \kappa\sqrt{x}$ with $\tau(n) > (\log x)^c$ is $o(\sqrt{x}/\log x)$. Together with Lemma 4, this implies

$$|\mathcal{Q}_a| \gg_a \frac{\sqrt{x}}{\log x}.$$

By Lemma 1, we have

$$\sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}_a} \left| \pi(x; q, a) - \frac{\pi(x)}{\varphi(q)} \right| \ll_a \frac{x(\log_2 x)^3}{(\log x)^3},$$

since $\varphi(q) \gg q/\log_2 q$. It follows that the number of $q \in \mathcal{Q}_a$ for which

$$\left| \pi(x; q, a) - \frac{\pi(x)}{\varphi(q)} \right| > \frac{\pi(x)}{2\varphi(q)} \gg \frac{x}{q \log x} \asymp \frac{\sqrt{x}}{\log x},$$

is

$$\ll_a \frac{\sqrt{x}(\log_2 x)^3}{(\log x)^2}.$$

Consequently,

$$|\mathcal{Q}'_a| \gg_a \frac{\sqrt{x}}{\log x},$$

where

$$\mathcal{Q}'_a = \left\{ q \in \mathcal{Q}_a : \left| \pi(x; q, a) - \frac{\pi(x)}{\varphi(q)} \right| \leq \frac{\pi(x)}{2\varphi(q)} \right\}.$$

For each $q \in \mathcal{Q}'_a$, the number of k such that $qk + a \leq x$ is prime, is

$$\pi(x; q, a) \geq \frac{\pi(x)}{2\varphi(q)} \gg \frac{x}{q \log x} \asymp \frac{\sqrt{x}}{\log x}.$$

The number of $k \leq \sqrt{x}$ for which $\tau(k) > (\log x)^c$ is $o(\sqrt{x}/\log x)$, by Lemma 2. Hence there are $\gg \sqrt{x}/\log x$ values of k for which $qk + a \leq x$ is prime and $\tau(k) \leq (\log x)^c$. Since $k \leq q$ and $q \in \mathcal{B}_0$, Lemma 3 shows that $qk \in \mathcal{B}_0$. Thus the number of pairs (q, k) such that $q \in \mathcal{Q}'_a$, $\tau(k) \leq (\log x)^c$ and $qk + a \leq x$ is prime, is

$$\gg \left(\frac{\sqrt{x}}{\log x} \right) \left(\frac{\sqrt{x}}{\log x} \right) = \frac{x}{(\log x)^2}.$$

For each of these pairs (q, k) , we have

$$\tau(qk) \leq \tau(q)\tau(k) \leq (\log x)^{2c},$$

which implies that there are at most $(\log x)^{2c}$ pairs (\tilde{q}, \tilde{k}) , such that $qk = \tilde{q}\tilde{k}$. It follows that the number of distinct elements of \mathcal{B}_0 of the form qk , for which $qk + a$ is prime, is

$$\gg \frac{x}{(\log x)^{2+2c}} = \frac{x}{(\log x)^\beta}.$$

□

3. The Upper Bound

Proposition 2. *Let $a \neq 0$ be fixed and $\delta = 1 - (1 + \log \log 2)/\log 2 = 0.086071\dots$. Let θ be an arithmetic function and $\theta(n)/n \leq h(n)$ for some non-decreasing h with $2 \leq h(x) \ll \sqrt{x}$. The number of primes $p \leq x$ such that $p - a \in \mathcal{B}_\theta$ is*

$$\ll \frac{x}{\log x} \left(\frac{2 \log h(x)}{\log x} \right)^\delta \left(\log \left(\frac{\log x}{\log h(x)} \right) \right)^{-3/2}.$$

The upper bounds in Theorem 2 follow from taking $h(n) = A \exp((\log n)^{o(1)})$ and $h(n) = \exp(A(\log \log 3n)^{3/(2\delta)})$.

Proof. Let $\tilde{\theta}(n) = nh(n)$ such that $\theta(n) \leq \tilde{\theta}(n)$ for all $n \geq 1$. Write \mathcal{B}_1 to denote $\mathcal{B}_{\tilde{\theta}}$. Since $h(n)$ is non-decreasing, Theorem 4 of [19] shows that \mathcal{B}_1 is precisely the set of integers n whose divisors $1 = d_1 < d_2 < \dots < d_{\tau(n)} = n$ satisfy

$$d_{j+1} \leq \tilde{\theta}(d_j) \quad (1 \leq j < \tau(n)).$$

We have $d_{j+1} \leq \tilde{\theta}(d_j) = d_j h(d_j) \leq d_j h(x)$ for every $n \in [1, x] \cap \mathcal{B}_1$, $1 \leq j < \tau(n)$. It follows that every $n \in (\sqrt{x}, x] \cap \mathcal{B}_1$ has a divisor in the interval $(\sqrt{x}, \sqrt{x}h(x)]$. We get

$$\begin{aligned} & |\{p \leq x : p \text{ prime, } p - a \in \mathcal{B}_\theta\}| \\ & \leq |\{p \leq x : p \text{ prime, } p - a \in \mathcal{B}_1\}| \\ & = |\{n \leq x - a : n + a \text{ prime, } n \in \mathcal{B}_1\}| \\ & \leq \sqrt{x} + |\{n \leq x + |a| : n + a \text{ prime, } n \text{ has a divisor in } (\sqrt{x}, \sqrt{x}h(x)]\}| \\ & \ll \frac{x}{\log x} \left(\frac{2 \log h(x)}{\log x}\right)^\delta \left(\log \left(\frac{\log x}{\log h(x)}\right)\right)^{-3/2}, \end{aligned}$$

where the last estimate follows from combining Theorem 1(v) and Theorem 6 of Ford [4]. □

Acknowledgments. We wish to thank Bill Banks for many helpful suggestions. This work began while the second author was visiting the University of Missouri. He thanks the Department of Mathematics for their hospitality and support.

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